

Methodological Considerations and Design of a comparative multi-case study investigating leadership for inclusion and social justice through collaborative professionalism in two primary mainstream schools in Greece and England.

Lito Vera Fouki

Lito.fouki2@mail.dcu.ie

Abstract

The focus of this paper is to describe the key methodological considerations underpinning the design of this research study which investigates the way school leaders promote inclusion and social justice through collaborative professionalism in two mainstream primary schools in England and Greece. Qualitative methods are described along with the ontological and epistemological dispositions of the researcher which informed how data was collected and how they were understood. The knowledge gathered from principals, teachers, parents and students during the interviews was unique and was developed and understood in different ways according to the participant's experiences, circumstances and perceptions. The ethical considerations, researcher positionality along with the trustworthiness of the study are also explored. A qualitative, comparative multi case study approach was used to explore in detail the research questions. The point of comparing each educational system was not to come to conclusions about which one is better, but to provide information about both countries and influence one another. One of the aims was to help "construct" a map which would include important information about inclusive education in two countries as a part of a bigger worldwide map.

Keywords

Methodology, Comparative multi case study, Researcher positionality, Validity, Epistemology, Ethical considerations, Inclusive Education

3 Main Highlights

- **Significance of Comparison:** The importance of the comparison is not to implement a foreign system in another country with different socioeconomic, political and cultural background, but for both countries to become role models for each other and influence positively their educational systems.
- **Content Validity:** Before attempting to translate the research questions, a colleague from a Greek school with years of experience in the educational system was asked to revise the questions to ensure accuracy, clarity and confirm the content validity in Greek during the pilot phase.
- **Philosophical Underpinnings/Epistemology:** The constructionist approach in this study is believing that the truth about the role of a leader or the collaborative cultures and practices that promote inclusion is the by-product of the individuals' knowledge and interactions combined (Hays & Singh, 2012).

Introduction

The aim of the methodology described in this paper is to support the topic under investigation, which is "*The role of school leadership in promoting inclusion and social justice in mainstream primary schools through collaborative professionalism: A comparative multi case study in England and Greece*". More specifically, the focus of this paper is on the research rationale, the research context, the research problem, the research questions, the aims and the significance of the study, the research design, the philosophical assumptions, the positionality of the researcher, the ethical considerations, the trustworthiness of the study.

Research Rationale

Inclusion could be described as ‘the careful and thoughtful marriage of educational excellence, equity and social justice’ (Pelletier, Powell, Bartlett, and Kusama-Powell, 2010, p. 6). Embracing and understanding all individual differences, including culture, race, gender, socioeconomic status and disability lies at the centre of its philosophy (Carrington, 1999). Inclusion is closely connected with a socially just society that addresses and eliminates marginalisation, poverty and racism. Both Greece (in 2012) and England (in 2009) have signed and ratified the UNCRPD (Genova, 2015, Conner, 2016) and SDG4 (Hellenic Republic, 2018, HM Government, 2019). Even though both countries have signed and seem to have agreed to the vision of inclusion and social justice, there is less clarity on how this is enacted in practice. There are many ways to approach inclusion but this study adopts a specific lens to explore it.

One approach to inclusive practices is collaborative professionalism (CP) (Hargreaves, 2019), which is about collaborative enquiry, action and collaborative responsibility. This approach focuses on the way teachers, other staff members and members of the community collaborate effectively for the success of all students.

Another aspect of education that is close to inclusion and social justice is leadership which also plays a vital role in school improvement, the quality of students’ experience inside and outside school (Angelides, Antoniou and Charalambous, 2010; Chapman, Ainscow, Miles, and West, 2011; Spillane and Diamond, 2007) and in developing and sustaining teachers’ professional learning for inclusive practice (King, 2011). The term leadership is a highly debated one; it is not only about one leader giving instructions to members of staff (Palaiologou and Male, 2011), it is about guiding and advising people to make the right decision to create collaborative cultures which are central to promoting inclusive practice (Ainscow and Sandill, 2010, MacRuairc, 2016). In essence, it is a collaborative endeavour centred around collaborative interactions (MacBeath et al., 2018). Despite the knowledge

around the importance of leadership and collaborative practice for inclusion there remains a gap between theory and practice which this study aims to address (Messiou, 2016).

Figure 1: Ten Tenets of Collaborative Professionalism

Figure 2: The Four Basic Concepts of the Study

The connection of the four basic concepts for this study can be understood better from the figures above. The ten tenets (Figure 1) helped in connecting the four overarching concepts (how *Leadership* can create opportunities for *CP* that can lead to more *inclusive practices*, closer to a more *socially just society* (Figure 2). The Ten tenets (Hargreaves, 2019) also informed the research and interview questions for the participants. They have been used to identify what collaborative practices happen in the schools, if they happen at all, how they are linked with the leader's practices and views on inclusion and what impact they have in the school life of the students in relation with the school community and in wider society. Lastly, they helped filter and clarify the understanding and enactment of inclusion in relation to social justice and the

practices of leadership. They also guided me in the design of the methodology, the methods, the research questions and the nature of the philosophical assumptions of this study.

Research Context

The most recent policies in Greece (Law 4547/2018) and England (Children and Families Act, special educational needs and Disability Code of Practice) (GOV.UK, 2014) regarding special educational needs provision theoretically have set the framework for a more inclusive school based on the educational needs and school reality of each country. According to the latest Greek educational policy 4547 (Special Education Needs Provision within Mainstream Education - Eurydice - European Commission, 2021) support is either provided by the parallel support teacher in the mainstream classroom or by attending a separate classroom, the inclusive classroom specific hours per week, thus highlighting the importance of collaboration between staff members. In England, on the other hand, the provision includes the involvement of local authorities, parents and students in the school community for a better and effective collaboration of all stakeholders to support the students. However, policies alone, without the guidance of effective leaders do not help create and sustain effective inclusive and socially just cultures (Robinson, 2010). Evidence from literature demonstrates that the success of inclusion is directly linked to the style of leadership (Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, 2008). The creation of inclusive cultures in schools is hindered when teachers are not trusted to become the leaders themselves, when there is non- inclusive curriculum, when there is lack of teacher training, lack of planning time and very limited time for sharing expertise and liaising with staff and the wider community.

Research Problem

Supporting staff members in all sectors requires school leaders who understand, value and promote an inclusive ethos (Sciullo, 2016). School leaders are in a unique position to

influence collaboration among teachers and other stakeholders. However, they may not be equipped to perform this role adequately (Balyer, Karatas and Alci, 2015).

That calls for the need of a better, more organic leadership model that allows teachers to become leaders themselves, that promotes collaborative cultures, inclusive ethos, social justice and is in constant and direct interaction with the needs of a wider community that answers the needs of its society. The distributed leadership model that leads to transformation of education and society could possibly be the answer to the needs of both countries and this is what this study tried to investigate.

Research questions

Consistent with the aims of the study, the following research questions were posed for investigation:

- How do school leaders in mainstream primary schools in Greece and England currently understand and enact inclusion?
- To what extent do school leaders promote inclusive practice in mainstream primary schools in Greece and England?
- To what extent are collaborative practices evident in supporting inclusion and social justice in Greece and England?
- How do parents and students with SEN understand and practise inclusion and social justice in mainstream schools in Greece and England?

Aim/Significance of the study

The focus of the study is to explore and compare the commitment towards inclusive education in two countries, Greece and England. It attempts to analyse how inclusion and social justice are promoted by leadership. Exploring the commitment and enactment of inclusion in these

different contexts will arguably support the international call for collaborative approaches to inclusive practice (Ainscow and Sandill, 2010).

Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological concept views school as a microsystem embedded within a macro-regional or national education system. At a micro and meso level this study provides the opportunity to school leaders and other staff members to reflect as individuals and as teams, and discuss the aspects of inclusive education. That could possibly result in reviewing the school's ethos and policies in both countries. School leaders then could possibly organise staff meetings with collaborative professionalism and special educational needs (SEN) as a topic and more voices could be heard, ideas and thoughts shared that could lead to change. It could be seen as an opportunity to share the needs of the students with SEN with the leadership team, hear their voices and start making suggestions for change. At a macro/exo level (national and international), this study also explores the dialogue between the two countries. With the word dialogue the research relationship between Greece and England is described. England could become a role model for Greece and vice versa. The key point of this is not to implement a foreign system in another country with different cultural background, economic and political state and of course different value system as this could have a high risk of failing, but for both countries to influence positively their educational systems, learn from each other and work towards better practices in different settings. The findings and recommendations of this study are expected to create an international map which, based on the conclusions about leadership for inclusion and social justice through collaborative professionalism, could provide a strong basis for future reference and improvement on the topic. One of the most important purposes of this study is also to cover any gap in terms of collaborative professionalism and inclusion, resulting possibly in policy changing. In the future other researchers could add more data about other countries and draw more attention to creating collaborative and inclusive cultures in schools. Comparative studies

tend to create more debate between countries and therefore enhance the dialogue for improving policies (Booth and Ainscow, 1998), while at the same time this may lead to a better understanding of one's own system (Crossley and Broadfoot, 1992). According to Messiou (2016) there should be a greater wave of studies that go further than describing problems with inclusion without changing them. The comparative nature of the study played a major part in the structure of the whole methodology.

Philosophical Assumptions

There are many different ways to view and interpret the world and its phenomena and in this paper I will present and justify my personal point of view and rationale for the subject under research. Ontology is about what we might know in reality (Robson, 2011), what is the nature of real life. It deals with assumptions which are “concerned with the very nature or essence of the social phenomena under investigation” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011, p. 6). An interpretivist/relativist ontological stance was adopted for this study. As this research focused on interviewing participants and gathering data mostly from people's perspectives on the role of the school leadership on inclusion and social justice, their perceptions were considered subjective and personal. According to the interpretivist paradigm, the opposite side of post positivism, I tried to assess and translate the participants' actions through a social lens (Usher, 1997). I was also conscious that participants are unique beings with subjective opinions and principles, and that reality and truth changes and adapts to time change, therefore it cannot be one, only and objective as proposed in post positivism (Hennink Hutter and Bailey, 2011). For interpretivists, reality is a construct in which people understand reality in different ways. So I, as an interpretivist, aimed to ‘describe and translate’ the subject from the perspective and experiences of head teachers, other leaders, teachers, parallel support teachers, parents and students in relation to inclusion. The more opinions I got, the better I could evaluate and explore the topic under investigation. This enhanced the triangulation of the data which also

raised the trustworthiness of the study.

This aligned with my epistemological assumption. The epistemology of my research that best suited my paradigm and aligned with my ontological stance was that from a constructionist approach. Epistemology, or the study of knowledge, is “a way of understanding and explaining how I know what I know” (Crotty, 1998, p. 3). It was chosen as I felt it best suited my research; that is exploring the social phenomena in the reality I live in and wish to discover (Robson, 2011). Constructionism is similar to constructivism in a sense that people make sense of their world through knowledge construction (Robson, 2011). However, constructionism is mostly about the way that the group understands the world they live in, while constructivism is concerned with the individual. This research therefore subscribed to the constructionist approach believing that the truth about the role of a leader or the collaborative cultures and practices that promote inclusion is the by-product of the individuals’ knowledge and interactions combined (Hays and Singh, 2012).

Research Design

A qualitative approach to research aligned with my philosophical stance as outlined above. The study aimed at comparing and interpreting the way the school leaders promote inclusion and social justice through collaborative professionalism in two mainstream schools in the UK and Greece. In order to achieve this, many qualitative research approaches were examined in order to determine the appropriate design for this study, but only two were selected that fitted the purpose and research question of this study; a case study and comparative design (Bryman, 2012).

A case study is described as an intensive qualitative research approach from a single case sample and the comparative design is seen as a “qualitative interview research on two or more

cases” (Bryman, 2012, p.76). This mix of designs is called “multi-case study”, as it compares more than one case. Case studies investigate a contemporary phenomenon within its real- life context and multiple sources of evidence are used for a more truthful and clear result (Yin, 2011). Case studies are a preferred strategy when the “how” and “why” questions are posed as the focus is on the process and the outcomes (Yin, 1994) reflecting the key aims of this study. In this specific study, the voices of the school leaders and staff members, parents and students provided a more holistic point of the reality. It also allowed me to put aside as many presumptions as possible in order to objectively explore the lives, culture and experiences of the participants (Stake, 1995).

Why Comparative?

The comparative nature of this study meets one of the aims of this research which is to compare the two educational systems and realities. This section focuses on the comparative aspect of the study and its importance in the comparative education field.

The focus of the comparison is to unearth and explore the historical and contemporary processes that have produced a sense of shared place, goal or identity to the topic investigated (Bartlett and Varvus, 2017). Comparative case studies tend not to ignore valuable contextual information, such as historical circumstances or imposing concepts (van der Veer, 2016). On the contrary, they seek to disrupt dichotomies, static categories or predetermined notions and concepts of the situations (Heath and Street, 2008). Despite the fact that both countries were European, there were major cultural differences in each context. Factors like the language, discourse, policies and social factors and interactions were taken into deep consideration when comparing. The Greek system has always been a strictly centralised system that allowed very little space for school leaders to initiate change, while in England schools have a relative freedom regarding managing their finances and school policy allowing them to act as

independent units and fund specific areas of the school. The relationship amongst school leaders and their power positions has also a comparative dimension since the provision made by different authority systems and the 'participation' of different groups in policy-making differed as well (Fulcher, 1989). Taking that into consideration, the comparative dimension provided a strong basis for exploration of the limitations and freedom to act for more inclusive practices.

Positionality

Positionality pertains to researchers understanding “their own selves in the research, seeking to understand their part in, or influence on, the research” (Cohen et al., 2011, p. 225) as “all writing is positioned” and “within a stance” (Creswell, 2007, p. 179). Considering the above for my study, I thought of myself as an insider and I chose to explore the pros and cons of “insiderness”. In my study I engaged in less intimate insider research, as it had been four years since I left the English school and many more since I left Greece. I also chose not to share my personal views, in order to avoid any bias to the participants. I only nodded or showed that I was listening to their views as I wanted to develop a level of trust in order for the participants to feel more comfortable and share their true views (Oakley, 1981, Logan, 1984). With regards to familiarity, insiders have a better understanding of the social setting as they know the context and they can assess the situations and events better (Griffiths, 1985). Having said that, insiders are also more likely to take things for granted and develop “myopia” and believe that others adopt their perspectives. Insider researchers may have the advantage of having easier access and greater rapport, but also have to keep in mind that their informants might have known them for too long, and thus have formed preconceptions about them or their research. Again, in my study the long absence from both educational settings and the lack of contact with most interviewees, created a gap in these relations with the participants and has worked in my favour regarding these biases. This approach matched my

constructionist stance where I wanted the participants to build their own reality based on their experiences and opinions.

Ethical considerations

One of the first responsibilities that I had to take care of was to gain ethical approval from DCU and consent to undertake research in the English school and the Greek school. Gaining consent from the Greek school was far more complicated due to the fact that the consent had to be processed and signed by the Minister of Education. It was a very long process that lasted more than three months. The whole procedure began in January 2018. Regarding the interviews with students with SEN, I had to make sure to use child friendly language and visual methods for students with speech, language and communication difficulties. Another major challenge was to get consent forms from parents of the students interviewed. I had to make a list of the students to be interviewed and then ask for parental consent. Also, the literature review and the pilot phase helped with clarifying the inclusion and exclusion criteria that I had to keep in mind when interviewing or observing during data collection.

Trustworthiness of Qualitative Research

As the case study consists of a unique context, principles of validity, reliability and generalisability were followed in undertaking this research such as avoidance of bias and ensuring transparency of the findings, strengthened by evidence and triangulation of data (Cohen et al., 2011). Unlike quantitative research, where reliability and validity are operationalized so rigidly, the challenge for me as a qualitative researcher was “to find alternative ways of operationalizing them appropriate to the conditions and circumstances of flexible design research” (Robson, 2011, p. 156).

Validity and reliability

Dependability, a kin concept to reliability in quantitative research paradigm, is related to the consistency of the research and the degree to which it can be replicated. In this case it refers to the similarity of the evidence gathered if the study were repeated. However, even if someone repeated exactly the study, it would still be considered a “new” study, as the social world keeps changing (new events, new ideas may happen overnight) (Suter, 2012). The results could have been the same even though participants' experiences could be worded in a different way. The goal of reliability is to minimise errors and biases in a study (Yin, 2003). Dependability in this research is enhanced by qualitative strategies used such as rich documentation, coding and triangulation (Suter, 2012).

Credibility/internal validity

Credibility refers to the believability of the findings and is supported by evidence such as confirming evaluation of conclusions by the participants of the study, use of multiple sources of evidence and control of unwanted influence (Suter, 2012). The believability of the conclusions in this study was provided by the participants agreement to state their opinions and views in an honest way, the analysis of the sources of data and other interpretations on relevant theoretical models. Internal validity is about matching the research findings with reality. In the course of time as I interpreted the findings, reality was likely to change to some degree. In order to maximise the internal validity, the use of triangulation or multiple sources of data secured and verified my emerging data (Robson, 2011). The data for this study were collected over an eight-month period, so this short-term collection period added to the validity of the findings as reality has not changed a lot (Merriam, 2009).

Content validity

The method of data collection for this study was made clear and well-defined. Since the interview questions were developed in English, they required translation into Greek. Before

attempting this, the content validity of the Greek version needed to be checked. I asked a colleague from a Greek special school, with years of experience in mainstream settings and in a leadership position to revise the interview questions to ensure their accuracy and clarity. What I really wanted was to see if these questions would make sense if they were asked to Greek teachers. And since I no longer live in Greece and I am in less interaction and there is less follow up with the Greek reality, a person who lives and works within the Greek educational system and reality would be the most appropriate person for confirming the content validity during the pilot study phase.

Conclusion

The methodology of this study was analysed after exploring and understanding the conceptual framework, laws and current policies from the two countries. It clearly supported the significance of the comparison, which was for both countries to influence each other positively. After spending two weeks in Greece in April 2019 for the first phase (pilot phase), the usability, reliability/credibility/validity was established. My stay included one pilot interview with a colleague and reviewing the content validity of the study (research and interview questions). After this, one more pilot interview was conducted in English and one lesson observation in an English-speaking classroom in my current working setting in Germany. Later, during September 2019 the first data collection phase was conducted in the English school in England and then in the Greek school in Greece during December 2019. Between then and now the transcription of the interviews, observation notes and sociogram was completed underpinning the constructionist approach about inclusion. The next steps include the process of analysing the data using NVivo and thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The first results will help guide the memos and then the final findings and the discussion.

References

- Ainscow, M. and Sandill, A. (2010) 'Developing inclusive education systems: the role of organisational cultures and leadership', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 14(4), pp. 401-416.
- Angelides, P., Antoniou, E. and Charalambous, C. (2010) 'Making sense of inclusion for leadership and schooling: a case study from Cyprus' *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 13(3), pp.319-334.
- Balyer, A., Karatas, H. and Alci, B. (2015) 'School Principals' Roles in Establishing Collaborative Professional Learning Communities at Schools' *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197, pp.1340-1347.
- Bartlett, L. and Vavrus, F. (2017) 'Comparative Case Studies: An Innovative Approach' *Nordic Journal of Comparative and International Education (NJCIE)*, 1(1).
- Booth, T. and Ainscow, M. (2006) *From them to us*. London [u.a.]: Routledge.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (2009) *Ecology of Human Development*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2012) *Social research methods*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Carrington, S. (1999) 'Inclusion needs a different school culture', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 3(3), pp.257-268.
- Chapman, C., Ainscow, M., Miles, S. and West, M. (2011) *Leadership that promotes the achievement of students with special educational needs and disabilities*, University of Manchester.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2011) *Research methods in education*. 7th edn. Milton Park, Oxon: Routledge.

Conner, L. (2016) 'Reflections on inclusion: how far have we come since Warnock and Salamanca?' *Research in Teacher Education*. 6 (1), pp. 18-23.

<https://doi.org/10.15123/PUB.5096>

Creswell, J. and Plano Clark, V. (2007) *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Crossley, M. and Broadfoot, P. (1992) 'Comparative and International Research in Education: scope, problems and potential', *British Educational Research Journal*, 18 (2), pp. 104-114.

Crotty, M. (1998) *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. London: Thousand Oaks, Calif: Sage Publications.

Eurydice - European Commission. (2021) *Special Education Needs Provision within Mainstream Education* - Eurydice - European Commission. [online] Available at: https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/special-education-needs-provision-within-mainstream-education-27_en (Accessed: 4 May 2019).

Fulcher, G. (1989) *Disabling Policies*. Lewes, Falmer Press.

Genova, A. (2015) 'Barriers to inclusive education in Greece, Spain and Lithuania: results from emancipatory disability research' *Disability & Society*, 30 (7), pp. 1042-1054.

GOV.UK. (2014) *Landmark Children and Families Act 2014 gains royal assent*. [online] Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/landmark-children-and-families-act-2014-gains-royal-assent> (Accessed: 14 June 2020).

Griffiths, G. (1985) *Doubts, dilemmas and diary-keeping: some reflections on teacher-based research*, in: R. Burgess (Ed.) *Issues in educational research: qualitative*

methods. London: The Falmer Press.

- Hargreaves, A. (2019) 'Teacher collaboration: 30 years of research on its nature, forms, limitations and effects', *Teachers and Teaching*, 25 (5), pp. 603-621
- Hays, D. and Singh, A. (2012) *Qualitative inquiry in clinical and educational settings*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Heath, S., Street, B. and Mills, M. (2008) *On ethnography*. New York: Teachers college Columbia university.
- Hellenic Republic, (2018) *Voluntary National Review on the Implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Greece*. [online] Gslegal.gov.gr. Available at: <https://gslegal.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/VNR-Greece-2018.pdf> (Accessed: 6 June 2020).
- Hennink, M.M., Hutter, I. and Bailey, A. (2011) *Qualitative Research Methods*. London: Sage Publications.
- HM Government, (2019) *Voluntary National Review of progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals*. [online] Assets.publishing.service.gov.uk. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/818212/UKVNR-web-accessible1.pdf (Accessed: 5 March 2020).
- King, F. (2011) 'The role of leadership in developing and sustaining teachers' professional learning', *Management in Education*, 25(4), pp.149-155.
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A. and Hopkins, D. (2008) 'Seven strong claims about successful school leadership', *School Leadership & Management*, 28(1), pp.27-42.
- Logan, T. (1984) *Learning through interviewing*, in J. Schoslak & T. Logan (Eds) *Pupil perspectives*. London: Croom Helm.
- MacBeath, J., Dempster, N., Frost, D., Johnson, G. and Swaffield, S. (2018) *Strengthening The Connections Between Leadership And Learning: Challenges to*

Policy, School and Classroom Practice. 1st edn. Routledge.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351165327>

MacRuairc, G. (2016) *Leadership for inclusive schools* [Webinar]. [online] Teachingcouncil.ie. Available at:

<http://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/Research/Research-Webinars/Leadership-for-Inclusive-Schools/> (Accessed: 29 November 2019).

Male, T. and Palaiologou, I. (2012) 'Learning-centred leadership or pedagogical leadership? An alternative approach to leadership in education contexts'. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 15(1), pp.107-118.

Merriam, S. (2009) *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons.

Messiou, K. (2016) 'Research in the field of inclusive education: time for a rethink?', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 21(2), pp.146-159. DOI: 10.1080/13603116.2016.1223184.

Morrison, M. (2002) *What do we mean by educational research? In: Coleman M and Briggs A (eds) Methods in Educational Leadership and Management*. London: Sage.

Oakley, A. (1981) *Interviewing women, in: H. Roberts (Ed.) Doing feminist research*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

Pelletier, K., Bartlett, W. and Kusama-Powell, K. (2010) *The Next Frontier: Inclusion In International Schools; A Practical Guide For School Leaders*. [online] Nextfrontierinclusion.org. Available at:

<http://www.nextfrontierinclusion.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/NFI-Practical-Guide-2nd-Edition.pdf> (Accessed: 14 June 2021).

Robinson, V. (2010) *From Instructional Leadership to Leadership Capabilities: Empirical Findings and Methodological Challenges*. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 9(1), pp.1-26.

Robson, C. (2011) *Real world research*. 3rd edn. Oxford: Wiley Publications.

Sciullo, J. (2016) *The Role of the School Leader in Collaboration Between Regular and Special Education Teachers*. [online] ODU Digital Commons. Available at: https://digitalcommons.odu.edu/efl_etds/12 (Accessed: 1 September 2020). DOI: 10.25777/rmjr-ft07.

Spillane, J. and Diamond, J. (2007) *Distributed leadership in practice*. New York: Teachers College, Columbia University.

Stake, R. (1995) *The art of case study research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Suter, W. N. (2012) *Qualitative data, analysis, and design*. In Suter, W. N. *Introduction to educational research: A critical thinking approach*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, pp.342-386., Inc. doi: 10.4135/9781483384443

UNESCO, (1994) *The Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education adopted by the World Conference on Special Needs Education: Access and Quality, Salamanca, Spain, 7-10 June 1994*. Paris: Unesco.

Usher, R. (1997) Telling a story about research and research as story-telling: Postmodern approaches to social research. In MCKENZIE, G., POWELL, J. and USHER, R. (eds.) *Understanding Social Research: Perspectives on Methodology and Practice*. London: Falmer Press.

van der Veer, P. (2016) *The value of comparison*. Durham: Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822374220>

Yin, K. (1994) *Case study research: design and methods*. Newbury Park, California.: Sage publications.

Yin, R. (2011) *Qualitative research from start to finish*. 1st edn. New York: Guilford Press.

Yin, R. (2003) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks: Sage.